

CATEGORY "TRANSITIONAL NATURE OF THE MOVEMENT" IN THE CODEX CUMANICUS MANUSCRIPT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7751177>

Abstract. *The study examines the category of the verb "transitional character of movement", manifested in terms of pronunciation. The purpose of the article is to unify the meaning of the category "transitional nature of movement" (A.Iskakov, M.Zholshayeva, N.Oralbayeva, Z.Akhmetzhanova, KTMukhamadi) with comments on the sound as a result of the analysis of verbal categories in the Kazakh language. To achieve this goal, it is planned to consider the meaning of the category "transitional nature of movement" in the ancient Turkic language, namely the use of this category in the Codex Cumanicus manuscript.*

The article presents a model for describing the differences of verbs included in the semantic group of the category "transitional character of movement" in the Kazakh language. The general and individual principles of the processes of semantic development of the category "transitional nature of movement" are defined. The description of the category "transitional nature of movement" in the modern Kazakh language complements the picture of the life process conveyed by the expression of movement. The authors of the article come to the conclusion that the specifics of the verb, expressing the transitional nature of the action, are better considered within the framework of a comparative historical grammar with indigenous languages. They come to the conclusion that an attempt to compare it with the Kazakh language due to the lack of features in unrelated groups of the language can distract attention from the study and prevent making the right conclusions.

In the course of the study, based on the collected vocabulary material using the method of classification of lexico-semantic groups of the verb of the category "transitional character of movement", semantic analysis and grouping by differentiated features were carried out.

The results of the research work can be guided in solving topical issues related to the field of historical grammar, expanding the field of general and applied language sciences, systematization of opinions related to the history of language.

Keywords: *Codex Cumanicus manuscript, historical grammar, modern Kazakh language, word classes, verb categories.*

Introduction. A special grammatical category of the verb that shows various features of the creation of an action, its stages from the beginning to the end is the transitive nature of the action. Researches related to the transitive nature of the movement provide an opportunity to study special categorial features of the verb.

Methodology and research methods. Although the transitive character of the verb as an independent grammatical category of the verb was recognized in Turkic studies, including Kazakh

language education, only in the second half of the 20th century, various peculiarities in the creation of the movement were noticed by researchers of Turkic languages from early times. For example, I. Giganov, who studied the Tatar language, in his work "Grammar of the Tatar language" used verbs: 1. Simple; 2. Complex verbs are divided into groups. The scientist says that most complex verbs consist of two verbs, the first of which is in the case of -p, -a, -e, -y. And it is concluded that the second conjugation of complex verbs gives the meaning of "prepositions" in the Russian language. For example, it is said that the meaning of the preposition "do" in the Russian language, which means the end of the action, is given by the auxiliary verbs "butamin, butaramin" in the Tatar language: "kayip botarde, yanyap bote" [1, 171]. Since this work is intended for learners of the Tatar language, we notice that more attention is paid to the practical problems of the language than to the theoretical problems. In this work, the indicators representing various features of the creation of the movement are not considered in order according to the language system. This problem is approached only from the point of view of showing the ways of the meaning of prepositions in the Russian language in the Tatar language. The characteristic category of the verb is not fully considered in the work written in comparative grammar. It can be seen that the goal of the scientist was on the other side.

In the research work "Grammatics of the Altai language" the peculiarities of the construction of actions in the Altai language are considered under the heading "The way of expression of the Russian "kinds" and verbs in the Altai language." The authors of the grammar say that the conjugation of verbs in the Altaic language with a preposition means the concept of "species" and "prepositions" of the verb in the Russian language [2, 184]. At the same time, the verbs in the Altai language stand alone as the beginning and end of the action, etc. emphasizes that it does not indicate a state. "Beginning, continuation, end of the movement" indicates that the verb is formed by combining certain verbs. For example, the verbs par-, kal-, sal-, koi-, al-, per- indicate the end of the action in the Altai language when they are attached to a connecting preposition, and he gives a separate example for each of them. For example, he says that the verb "sheep" means the end of the action, and gives the following example: His body was dug up in the ground [2, 188] The authors of "Altai Language Grammar" are also Altai. He paid attention to the ways of expressing various peculiarities in the creation of actions in the language, comparing them with the Russian language, and what are the ways of conveying the meaning of prepositions in the Altai language. That is, the authors intended to show the similarities and differences of the Altaic language with the Russian language only by comparison.

Academician V.A. Gordlevsky in his research work "Grammar of the Turkish language" talks about the various features of the creation of the action in the Turkish language under the special topic "Transmission of shades of actions": "Various shades of the action (usually the first one is in the prepositional person) are given by combining two verbs" [3, 102] . . In the research of the scientist, the transitive nature of the verb category in the Turkic languages has been somewhat revealed. However, it can be seen that the authors did not completely distinguish some signs of the meaning of the verb because they did not have their own language.

Discussion and observation. In Soviet Turkic studies, since the thirties of the 20th century, the opinion prevailed that Turkic languages have a category of "vid" like Slavic languages. Scientists such as V. A. Bogoroditskyi, N. K. Dmitriev, A. Borovkov, I. A. Batmanov, N. P. Dyrenkova, A. Kharisov, L. N. Kharitonov, and N. A. Baskakov have pointed out the differences in the creation of gestures in Turkic languages. justified the point of view that the expression of

peculiarities is the same as the category "vid" in the Russian language. The overwhelming majority of those who believe that there is a category of "vid" in Turkic languages indicate the end stage of the action as a finished scene. For example, A. Borovkov mentions the category "vid" in the Uyghur language in the title "Textbook of the Uyghur language" [4, 172]. The scientist does not reveal how many types of "vid" there are in the Uyghur language. He says that the verbs in the Uyghur language have nothing to do with "vid" no matter what tense they are: "The concepts of the completeness of the action appear in the Uyghur language in a descriptive way, through special auxiliary verbs" [4, 175]. As we have seen, A. Borovkov believes that auxiliary verbs in the Uyghur language add an additional meaning to them by forming the ending "vid" like prefixes in the Russian language. The scientist points out that auxiliary verbs such as koi-, kal-, al-, bar-, kat, kol-, shik-, bol, which indicate the end of the action in the Uyghur language, form the completed "vid". For example, it is said that the auxiliary verb "be" in the Uyghur language indicates the complete completion of the action [4, 176]. A. Borovkov focused on only one "vid" in the Uyghur language, that is, the completed "vid". And he did not say that this auxiliary verb combines with other suffixes and changes its meaning.

In his work "Grammatical aspects of the Kyrgyz language " examines the category "vid" in the Kyrgyz language under the title "About the category of Hades". The scientist believes that there are finished, unfinished, one-time and several-time occurrences in the meaning of the main verb [5, 10]. However, "however, the variations of these types do not have strict norms and change depending on the context of speech" [5, 10], saying that the type of "vid" varies depending on the text, shows that the scientist was not able to come to a conclusion on this issue. Recognizing the ending of the action in the Kyrgyz language as a completed "vid" is also characteristic of I.A. Batmanov: "In addition, the category of the perfect form is replaced by other variations of the meaning: the direction of the action and its relation to the agent of the action, etc. b. This shadow of the course of action or nature of action is given by the combination of the main auxiliary verb and the participle (-п, -ып, -ип, -уп, -ип) form of the main verb" [7, 10]. The scientist says that the completed "vid" in Kyrgyz is formed by joining the auxiliary verbs bol-, al-, bir-, khiz-, jiber-, ket-, kal, kel-, kai- to the prefix -п [5, 37]. From this differentiation of the scientist, it can be seen that he did not completely reveal the category of the nature of the verb in the language. It is noteworthy that I.A. Batmanov called the additional meanings related to the completed "vide" also "characters of action" . At the same time, he thinks about the passing nature of the movement. Although the scientist correctly understood the peculiarities of the nature of the language, he could not get out of the influence of the traditional view of the species that was formed in Turkic studies before him. In his analysis, scientists before him can prove the features of the common character category in Turkic languages only with examples. As mentioned above, the opinion of well-known Turkic scholars that Turkic languages have the same species category as in Russian prompted the writing of special research works on this issue in separate Turkic languages. For example, A. Kharisov wrote a monograph entitled "Category of Verb Forms in Bashkir". The scientist says about the vid category in this article: "The vid category in the Bashkir language means the form and path of the action (state) given in the verb, and considering the action as a stream, on the one hand, it shows its appearance at the beginning, continuation (uninterrupted or continuous in its development) or at the end, or on the other hand on the other hand, it provides a quantitative description of the action in it" [6, 11]. Version in Bashkir by A. Kharisov: 1. Initial appearance; 2. Chronic appearance; 3. The finished view is divided into three parts by [6, 11]. The scientist must

have connected the types of appearance with the stages of movement development. Because there is no tradition of classifying species in this way in Russian language education. That is, for the first time, A. Kharisov made a correct judgment about the peculiarities of Turkic languages. For the first time, the Turkic languages show their originality, not only in comparison with the Russian language. But even this could not fully reveal the transitive nature of the action in the verb.

Doubts whether there is a species category of verbs in Turkic languages, just like in Russian. First of all, the scientist objects to the division of verb forms in Turkic languages into three types: "initial, long, final form": "Such a division cannot be accepted due to the following two reasons: firstly, the appearance of the verb is a qualitative-quantitative semantic category of the verb in expressing an action or state, and secondly, shows that the development and creation of the movement is not a spatial description, but a temporal description [7, 33]. The scientist rightly notices that the expression of various features of the movement in the Turkic languages is different from the *vid* category in the Russian language. V.M. Nasilov describes the function of a number of auxiliary verbs that indicate various peculiarities in the creation of a movement in the Uyghur language, and expresses the opinion that the diversity of the description of the movement requires systematization [7, 52]. As we have seen, scientists tried to express key ideas based only on the grammatical features of the Russian language. And he did not take into account that there is no grammatical similarity between the Turkic languages and the Russian language. Later, it is known that the Russian language scholars' desire to connect all language categories with the Russian language was also used in the analysis of the grammatical system of the Kazakh language. N.A. Baskakov also focuses on the species category in the Karakalpak language in his work "Karakalpak language" [8, 352]. Scientist N.K. Dmitriev believes that the completed form and incomplete form belong to the tense category in Turkic languages [8, 353]. N.A. Baskakov calls the indicators of various peculiarities in the creation of the movement, which are called the transition characteristics of the movement in Turkic studies, and divides them into two groups: A. Species that determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the verb; B. Types that describe the durational character of the verb, the beginning and end of the movement, as well as its direction in space and time [8, 353]. As we can see, the scientist's opinion was somewhat correct only when looking at the Turkic roots.

The variety of opinions of Turkic language researchers about the type category of verbs in Turkic languages caused this issue to be put as a special issue on the agenda of the Coordination Council of Turkic Studies held in 1956. However, even in this council, Turkicologists could not come to a decision on whether or not Turkic languages have the same category of verbs as in Russian. Academician B. A. Serebrennikov, who made a special report on this issue, proved that there is no type category of verbs in Turkic languages, as in Russian. The scientist points out that although the preposition and the auxiliary verb have the meaning of *vid*, they cannot form a category of appearance, because the ending and duration of the action are complicated by additional shades [9, 30]. On the contrary, A. Kharisov and I. E. Mamanov try to prove that there is a type category of verbs in Turkic languages. These two opinions continued in the following years. In the scientific works published in the early sixties, some scientists were still busy searching for the species category in Turkic languages. For example, L. N. Kharitonov in his monograph "Forms of verb types in the Yakut language" expressed his opinion that familiarization with the actual materials of the Yakut language shows that the traditional concept of verb types can be used in the Yakut language. The researcher says that instead of two types of appearance opposed to

each other in the Slavic language, the Yakut language shows 12 types of verb appearance [10, 8]. At the same time, after the above-mentioned consultation, some scientists tried to look at the nature of the linguistic phenomena called "vid" category in Turkic languages in a different way. For example, it can be seen that the opinion of the scientist A.N. Kononov about the species category of verbs in Turkic languages took on a new character after the Soviet Union. In his work "Grammar of the Modern Uzbek Literary Language", the scientist for the first time calls the ways of expressing various peculiarities in the creation of a gesture, which were mistakenly recognized as the category of type in Turkic studies, as the "category of the character of the transition of the gesture" [11, 263]. Although the scientist does not indicate the inner meaning of the transitive nature of the movement, he mentions the ways of its transmission in the Uzbek language: 1. Word combining method: consists of -ib and -a, -e, -y preposition and verb modifier; 2. Method of affixation. In the textbook "Grammar of the Kyrgyz language" the category of the transitive character of the action is considered in the special topic "Verb forms expressing the transitive difference of the action" [12, 290].

Results. Scientist N. Oralbaeva defines the category of transition character of the movement as follows: "This grammatical category means different meanings depending on the creation of the movement, how the movement was made and what stage and degree of the movement the speaker is communicating. We named this category with the term "transitional nature of movement" [13, 74]. N. Oralbaeva's naming of the category of verbs in the Kazakh language as "the nature of the transition of the movement" showed that researches related to the nature of the movement in Turkic languages in general should be reconsidered.

He divides the category of the transition character of the movement into two parts: the type of movement and the stage of development of the movement. The scientist shows the following meanings related to the creation of the movement: artificiality of the movement, imperfection, done with special enthusiasm, done carelessly, done unexpectedly, done at a special pace, done short and courageously, limitation of the movement, lack of haste of the movement, tendency to be done. Researcher: "The stage of development of a movement is its state from the beginning to the end." Just as the beginning of the movement is legal, the end of the movement should also be legal. If the started action has not reached its completion stage, then the action is in progress. Due to the development of movement, these peculiarities are called the first, second, third stage of movement" [13, 103]. In this way, the scientist mentioned the meaning forms of the transition of the movement in the Kazakh language. N. Oralbaeva in her scientific works written about the analytical formants of the verb shows the meaning of making a movement unexpectedly, suddenly, making a movement boldly, briefly, making a movement with a special pace (force) [13, 91]. And Z. Akhmetzhanova in her research work "Functional-semantic fields of Russian and Kazakh languages" shows 3 different shades of meaning from the way of quick movement. They are: one short action, sudden, unexpected action, and careless, easy action [14, 59]. Most of the later studies that differentiate the features of the transitive nature of the verb categories focus on the shades and internal division of the said category. The process of change of the movement - immediate, slow, continuous, progressive, sudden, speedy characteristics, incomplete and careless or enthusiastic, deliberate, beginning and end period is considered closely related to time, etc., which make the category of aspectuality a scientific basis. Scientists create the scientific foundations of the transitive character of the Kazakh language and focus on its formation and types. The aspectuality category expresses the transitive nature of the action and is created not only by the analytical

formants of the verb, but also by other linguistic units in the language system. All indicators in the language system are actively involved in expressing aspectual meaning. At the same time, there were also scientific works that studied the need to analyze the effect of the word on the expression of the meaning in the sentence, which is then considered with its contextual meaning.

Researcher K. T. Muhamadi in his dissertation work entitled "Meaning composition and ways of transmission of the speed of movement in the modern Kazakh language" shows the ways of transmission of the speed of movement. "As a result of a special study of the meaning of the speed method of movement, the following meaning groups were determined for this method: 1. Sudden movement; 2. Making a bold move; 3. Making a gesture at a pace; 4. Easy making of the gesture; 5. Making a gesture only once; 6. Short repetition of the gesture; 7. Rapid onset of movement [15, 85].

Scientist A. Yskakov shows two different ways of making a movement:

- 1) "... each of the synthetic forms represents a different and different nature of the action;
- 2) The second type of the category of the nature of the transition of the action - the analytical type is created by means of the analytical formants that have become established in our language" [16, 290].

Scientist N. Oralbaeva shows three ways of transmission of movement style:

- "1) Through the suffix: kuala, smile, etc.;
- 2) By reduplication of the root verb in the prepositional person: to jerk, etc.;
- 3) Through analytical formants" [13, 85].

Researcher K. T. Muhamadi in his dissertation work entitled "Meaning composition and ways of transmission of the speed of movement in the modern Kazakh language" shows three different ways of transmission of the speed of movement: 1) through analytical formants; 2) through the Koranic verbs from imitation words; 3) Transmission through lexical indirect indicators [15, 118].

In the "Codex Cumanicus" manuscript, there are many verbs formed by means of suffixes, which express the transitive nature of the action. For example, the verb kuvaladym is a positive, active, open tense. The root is ku, -a is the suffix of the preposition, -la is the verb-forming suffix, -dy is the immediate past tense suffix, -m is the participle in the first person [17].

Also, there is also the analytical formant -p, which means quick, short repetition of the action, which is attached to the secondary dual verb, indicating the quick execution of the action: **құлқу қуқу** - complex verb, immediate past tense, open mood. **Усқан** - the root is усқан, -p is the suffix of the preposition; Kaldym is the root kal, -dy is the suffix of the immediate past tense, -m is the participle in the first person [17].

Conclusion. In general, in Turkic studies, the category of the transitive character of the verb is recognized. However, there is no terminological consistency in the naming of the category that represents various features of the movement in the linguistic system. In Turkic studies, the category of the transitive nature of the movement has become the object of research not only from the point of view of traditional grammar, but also of applied grammar. In addition, it would be better to consider the feature of the verb, which expresses the transitive nature of the action, in the context of historical grammar in comparison with related languages. Due to the fact that Kazakh language does not have features that are found in unrelated groups of languages, trying to make it similar every day will turn the direction of the research and prevent correct conclusions. This is

evidenced by the above-mentioned divergent opinions of Russian scientists about the grammar of Turkic languages.

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